

ASSESSMENT AND EVALUATION MODELS

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HANDBOOK

ASSESSMENT AND EVALUATION MODELS

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KEYWORDS

Assessment and Evaluation Models; Survey; Multimedia; Interview; Types of Models; Presentation; Presenter;

ABSTRACT

This project has been funded with the support from the European Commission. This publication reflects the views only of the autor, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

This handbook contains all the information regarding to our theme, which is Assessment and Evaluation Models.

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GREETINGS FROM US

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WHAT IS IT?

Evaluation models are used to measure the effectiveness of a program, project, or initiative. There are several different models that can be used, depending on the purpose of the evaluation and the context in which it is being conducted.

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TYPES OF MODELS

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KIRKPATRICK MODEL

Was developed in 1950s and is widely used today. It has four levels of Evaluation: reaction, learning, behavior and results. This model, begins by measuring participants reactions to the program and then evaluates what they've learned. It also observes changes in their behavior and, finally measures de program's results.

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SCRIVEN MODEL

Is a comprehensive approach to evaluation that includes six steps: define the program, develop an evaluation plan, collect data, analyze data, report results , and act. This model is often used for large-scale evaluations, such as those conducted by government agencies or large corporations.

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STUFFLEBEAM'S CIPP MODEL

Stands for context, input, process and product. It evaluates a program based on the context in which it was implemented, the inputs or resources used, the process by which the program was implemented and the products or results of the program.

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ROI MODEL

Measures the return on investment of a program. It is commonly used in business settings to determine if a program is worth the cost.

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GOAL - FREE MODEL

Is used to evaluate a program without preconceptions about what the outcomes should be, it focuses on observing what happens during the program and evaluating its effectiveness based on those observations.

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LOGIC MODEL

Is used to map the inputs, activities, outputs and impacts of a program. It is often used in the planning stages of a program to ensure that all components are aligned and working towards the same goals.

INFOGRAPHIC 01

MODELS

KIRKPATRICK MODEL

The model begins by measuring participants' reactions to the program, then evaluates what they have learned, observes changes in their behavior, and finally measures the program's results.

01

SCRIVEN MODEL

This model is a comprehensive approach to evaluation that includes six steps: define the program, develop an evaluation plan, collect data, analyze data, report results, and take action.

02

STUFFLEBEAM'S CIPP MODEL

It evaluates a program based on the context in which it was implemented, the inputs or resources used, the process by which the program was implemented, and the products or results of the program.

03

LOGIC MODEL

It is often used in the planning stages of a program to ensure that all components are aligned and working towards the same goals.

04

ROI MODEL

This model measures the return on investment of a program. It is commonly used in business settings to determine if a program is worth the cost.

05

GOAL-FREE MODEL

This model focuses on observing what actually happens during the program and evaluating its effectiveness based on these observations.

06

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ASSESSMENT IN MULTIMEDIA

Multimedia assessment involves evaluating students' knowledge and skills in creating, manipulating and presenting multimedia content. This can include video, audio, graphics and animation.

Multimedia assessment can take various forms, including projects, portfolios, presentations and tests.

INFOGRAPHIC 02

ASSESSMENT IN MULTIMEDIA

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PRESENTATION CARE

For a very successful presentation it is important for you to consider that, there is a message to be delivered to an audience, that should follow basic communication rules.

Here are, a few steps to help you organize your presentations.

- 1 It is necessary to structure all the information in a document, that will serve as a guide throughout the entire presentation;
- 2 It is important to simplify the information and make it as concise as possible, using only key thoughts and highlighting the most relevant information or words;
- 3 Once you have all the information organized, you should be separated into themes or ideas, dividing it into different slides, with a maximum of 10 short sentences per slide.

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PRESENTATION CARE

- 4 When it comes to the fonts, it is ideal for you, to use one to two fonts for titles and the other for body text. The font size should be larger than 22, for the body and 40 for titles.
- 5 The visual aspect, regarding colors and image, it's essential, because they capture the audience's attention. Therefore, there should be a contrast between texts, images and background colors.
- 6 In case you are presenting for a company/brand, the PowerPoint should follow the company's logo guidelines and colors. Remember to not exceed three colors on the slides.
- 7 Regarding yet to the colors, keep in mind that, light colors express joy and dark colors express sadness. It is best to use neutral and soft colors.
- 8 When creating content for your presentation, consider the target audience as well as the copyrights of any content you may include, whether it be text, images or music.

INFOGRAPHIC 03

CARE TO BE TAKEN IN PRESENTATIONS

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SKILLED PRESENTER

It is necessary to prepare the speech in advance, so that, the references on the slides presentation be just a reference and not reading material.

Make sure, you always give a personal touch to the presentation, by providing innovative information and even sharing personal experiences that are relevant and relate to the presentation topic.

Plan your presentation to spend a maximum of two minutes per slide.

Maintaining an appropriate posture during a presentation is crucial. Your voice should be well projected so that all recipients can understand the message clearly. Maintain also eye contact with your audience.

Other important aspect is understanding the type of audience you are addressing and in the end, leave time for questions and clarification of doubts.

INFOGRAPHIC 04

SKILLED PRESENTER

Prepare the speech in advance so that it goes beyond repeating the message displayed on the PowerPoint slide. Otherwise, it may convey a sense of insecurity to the audience.

Strive to give a personal touch to the presentation by providing innovative information and even sharing personal experiences that are relevant and relate to the presentation topic.

Your voice should be well projected so that all recipients can understand the message being conveyed, and continuous eye contact should be maintained with the audience.

Plan your presentation to spend a maximum of two minutes per slide, balancing moments of speech with pauses.

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HOW TO BUILD A SURVEY

Define a Target Audience: Once you know the answers you want to receive, it's time to determine exactly who those responses should come from. Choosing the target audience for the survey will directly impact its success;

Keep it Simple: To obtain honest and genuine responses and make respondents identify with and care the survey, it is necessary to make it interesting. Keeping the questionnaire simple is crucial.

Explain the Purpose of the Survey: Explaining the reason behind the survey at the beginning helps maintain participants' engagement and interest.

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HOW TO BUILD A SURVEY

Use Familiar Language: This step directly relates to the first three points mentioned. Formulating questions that employ language that makes sense to respondents is crucial.

Formulate the questions: While formulating the questions may seem obvious, it should not be done without establishing certain parameters first, such as the objective, purpose, and target audience of the survey.

Use additional resources: There is no mandatory or rigid template for creating a research questionnaire. That's why it's common and advisable to use additional resources to complement the survey and improve respondent engagement, especially if the topic is more sensitive.

INFOGRAPHIC 05

HOW TO BUILD A QUESTIONNAIRE

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HOW TO PREPARE FOR AN INTERVIEW

Prepare Yourself: Not being properly prepared is a costly mistake. Preparing in advance for the company or the position you are applying for. Study the organization's website, read news about the company and research more about the interviewer to avoid this mistake.

Punctuality: Arriving late or missing the initial contact with the company, suggests a lack of interest in the opportunity presented and gives an unprofessional and unreliable impression. As a candidate, always try to confirm your attendance in advance and arrive slightly early, to make sure that everything goes as expected.

Highlight Your Skills: Asking questions about the company and the position, especially towards the end of the conversation, is one of the key points during a job interview. This attitude shows that you are genuinely interested in joining the company, understanding its day-to-day operations, as well as its values and mission.

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HOW TO PREPARE FOR AN INTERVIEW

Maintain Proper Posture: The candidate should avoid appearing careless or failing to make eye contact with the recruiters, as it may indicate negligence and insecurity. Dress appropriately for the occasion and avoid being too informal.

Attend Alone: An interview is a personal moment, so showing up with someone else is not advised. It's not recommended to bring an accompanying person and if, someone does accompany you, they should not intervene in the conversation on behalf the candidate.

INFOGRAPHIC 06

PRECAUTIONS TO TAKE IN AN INTERVIEW

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